

Self-Supervised Learning for 3D Medical Imaging: Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

Self-Supervised Learning for 3D Medical Imaging

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

SSL3D

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

This challenge seeks to identify the most effective self-supervised learning (SSL) method for 3D medical imaging. By standardizing critical factors such as pre-training dataset, network architecture, preprocessing pipelines, and fine-tuning schedules, the competition ensures a fair and transparent evaluation environment that allows to identify the best SSL pretext task for 3D medical imaging.

The development of SSL techniques for 3D medical imaging has been hindered by inconsistencies in research practices. Variability in pre-training dataset sizes, differences in network designs, and the use of diverse downstream evaluation datasets have created significant barriers to identifying the most effective methods. This lack of standardization complicates the comparison of approaches and limits progress in the field. This challenge seeks to overcome these obstacles by offering a common pre-training dataset and fine-tuning framework to fairly evaluate self-supervised pre-training strategies and drive innovation in 3D medical imaging.

Dataset Overview

Participants will have access to the largest publicly available head & neck MRI dataset derived from the publicly available OpenNeuro platform. This dataset is an amalgamation of over 700 smaller datasets, all published under a permissive CC0 or PDDL license. After cleaning and standardization of image format and metadata, the final dataset comprises 114,570 3D volumes from 34,191 patients. The collection contains a variety of well-established MRI sequences, such as T1w, Flair, T2w sequences, as well as diffusion coefficient (ADC) and fractional anisotropy (FA) maps. More details about the dataset can be found in the pre-print associated with this challenge <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2412.17041>.

Task Description

Participants can utilize two predefined network architectures: one based on convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and the other on transformer models. The objective is to develop SSL methods that enable these networks to learn robust and generalizable feature representations. Submissions will consist solely of the pre-trained

weights, which will be assessed through fine-tuning on at least 6 hidden head & neck MRI segmentation and classification tasks. These evaluation tasks will remain confidential to ensure an unbiased and standardized comparison of methods. The challenge participants will not have access to the private downstream datasets and the finetuning will be done by the challenge organizers.

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

Self-Supervised Learning, 3D medical image segmentation, 3D medical image classification

Year

2025

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

The novelty of this challenge lies in introducing and utilizing the largest publicly available dataset for 3D medical imaging to standardize the evaluation of self-supervised learning strategies. This dataset provides an unparalleled foundation for consistent experimentation, addressing the fragmentation seen in previous studies with varying and often limited datasets. By combining this comprehensive dataset with a controlled evaluation framework featuring fixed architectures and undisclosed downstream tasks, the challenge ensures fair comparison and introduces a new benchmark for advancing self-supervised learning in 3D medical imaging.

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

The results of this challenge will provide valuable insights into self-supervised learning methods applicable across all areas of medical image analysis. While these methods are developed on a head & neck MRI dataset, the methods are expected to be modality agnostic and should generalize to different 3D imaging modalities, such as CT, when trained on corresponding data. The models trained in scope of the challenge are expected to deliver particularly strong performance improvements for head & brain MRI downstream tasks, driving advancements in diverse and clinically significant applications.

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

-

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

2 Hours

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

-

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

Self-supervised learning on large-scale data has garnered significant attention in the medical imaging community, with increasing interest driven by its potential to leverage unlabeled data effectively. By providing a comprehensive dataset and an easy-to-use codebase integrated into the widely adopted nnU-Net framework, we significantly lower the entry barrier for participants. Based on our experience with previous challenges, we anticipate approximately 30 teams will participate.

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

A comprehensive challenge paper summarizing the results, insights, and key findings is planned.

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

A challenge webpage will be hosted on our own infrastructure, and participants will only submit pre-trained checkpoints. These checkpoints will be loaded and fine-tuned on our compute systems to ensure a fair and standardized evaluation. For the on-site event, we will require a projector, loudspeakers, and microphones to facilitate presentations and discussions.

TASK 1: Pre-training

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

This challenge seeks to identify the most effective self-supervised learning (SSL) method for 3D medical imaging. By standardizing critical factors such as pre-training dataset, network architecture, preprocessing pipelines, and fine-tuning schedules, the competition ensures a fair and transparent evaluation environment that allows to identify the best SSL pretext task for 3D medical imaging.

Participants can utilize two predefined network architectures: one based on convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and the other on transformer models. The objective is to develop self-supervised pretext tasks that enable these networks to learn robust and generalizable feature representations. Submissions will consist solely of the pre-trained weights, which will be assessed through fine-tuning on at least 6 hidden brain MRI segmentation and classification tasks. These evaluation tasks will remain confidential to ensure an unbiased and standardized comparison of methods.

The challenge is divided into two independent tracks, each focusing on a different architecture. For the CNN track, we use the ResenL architecture, recently introduced by Isensee, Wald, Ulrich, and Baumgartner et al. (2024). For the transformer track, we employ a ViT-inspired architecture specifically designed for 3D medical applications. While transformer-based architectures currently lag behind CNN-based architectures in performance [Isensee, Wald, Ulrich, & Baumgartner et al. 2024], extensive pre-training has the potential to narrow or even close this performance gap.

Participants are allowed to modify the architecture during pre-training to their liking. For instance, this can include adding task-specific heads, using different decoders, modifying normalization layers, adjusting positional embeddings, varying augmentation strategies, incorporating contrastive learning objectives, applying domain-specific pretext tasks, or implementing teacher-student approaches with the teacher being whatever architecture the participants prefer. However, for the downstream evaluation, the architectures will remain fixed, and the submitted pre-trained weights must be transferred, into the pre-defined architectures, hence need to be at least partially compatible.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Self-Supervised Learning, 3D medical image segmentation, 3D medical image classification

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Constantin Ulrich* [1,4,5], Tassilo Wald* [1,2,3], Yannick Kirchoff [1,2,13], Marcel Knopp [7,2], Robin Peretzke [1,4], Maximilian Fischer[1,4, 12], Partha Ghosh [1], Fabian Isensee[1,3], Paul Naser [9, 10], Lars Wessel [11], Martha Foltyn-Dumitru [8], Gianluca Brugnaral[1,8], Jan Oliver Neumann [9], Laila König [11], Philipp Vollmuth [1,8], Klaus Maier-Hein[1,2,3,4,5,6]

1 German Cancer Research Center (DKFZ) Heidelberg, Division of Medical Image Computing, Heidelberg, Germany

2 Faculty of Mathematics and Computer Science, University of Heidelberg, Germany

3 Helmholtz Imaging, DKFZ, Germany

4 Medical Faculty Heidelberg, University of Heidelberg, Germany

5 National Center for Tumor Diseases (NCT), NCT Heidelberg, A partnership between DKFZ and University Medical Center Heidelberg

6 Pattern Analysis and Learning Group, Department of Radiation Oncology

7 German Cancer Research Center (DKFZ) Heidelberg, Division of Intelligent Medical Systems, Heidelberg, Germany

8 Division for Computational Radiology & Clinical AI (CCIBonn.ai), Department of Neuroradiology, University Hospital Bonn, Germany

9 Department of Neurosurgery, University Hospital Heidelberg, Germany

10 AI Health Innovation Cluster, German Cancer Research Center (DKFZ), Heidelberg, Germany

11 Department of Radiation Oncology, University Hospital Heidelberg, Heidelberg, Germany

12 German Cancer Consortium (DKTK), partner site Heidelberg

13 HIDSS4Health - Helmholtz Information and Data Science School for Health, Karlsruhe/Heidelberg, Germany

*equal contribution

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

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Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI 2025

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

Own challenge website

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

ssl3d-challenge.dkfz.de

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

No additional data allowed

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

We currently have €1,000 in prize money and are seeking additional sponsors to reach at least €1,000 per track. Final prize amounts will be announced after acceptance. The prize money for each track will be distributed as follows: 1st Place: 50% 2nd Place: 30% and 3rd Place: 20%.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

Results of all participating teams will be announced on the challenge website and during an in-person event at the MICCAI 2025 conference.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

The authors of the top 3 winning teams will be invited to co-author the official challenge paper, which will summarize the results and key findings. To ensure transparency and reproducibility, all participating teams are required to share their code and provide a detailed technical description of their methods as part of their submission. Additionally, all teams are free to publish their results independently, and no embargo period will be enforced.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Participants will be provided with the codebase and corresponding network architectures. Submission will involve uploading only the pre-trained checkpoint files. Detailed submission instructions will be provided on the challenge website after acceptance.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Participants will have the opportunity to submit their pre-trained checkpoint once to a validation stage up to 2 weeks before the final submission deadline. This validation stage will allow teams to evaluate their preliminary results on three public datasets, helping them refine their methods before submitting final results. Since these test datasets are publicly available, this stage will continue to serve as a public benchmark beyond the challenge.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

April 1, 2025: Challenge website launch and training cases released.

July 30, 2025: Validation submission deadline.

August 15, 2025: Test submission deadline.

Late September 2025: Results announced at the associated MICCAI 2025 workshop.

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

No

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC-BY-4.0

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

Both the fine-tuning and ranking code will be made publicly available. The code will be based on the well-established nnU-Net framework [Isensee & Jaeger et al., 2021] and will adhere to best practices in challenge evaluation [Maier-Hein & Reinke et al., 2024; Maier-Hein & Eisenmann et al., 2020].

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

To be eligible for prizes, participating teams must publish their code under a permissive CC-BY license, ensuring accessibility, transparency, and reproducibility for the broader research community.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

The challenge will use private test sets, with labels and images not publicly accessible. Access to this data will be restricted to a limited number of researchers at the DKFZ, as well as clinical partners from the University Hospital Heidelberg and the University Hospital Bonn. To support the challenge, we aim to secure funding from major companies in the fields of medical imaging and data analysis; however, these companies will not have access to the test datasets.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education

- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Research

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Segmentation, Classification

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target cohort includes all patients undergoing an MRI head & neck scan, regardless of age, sex, or specific medical condition. The resulting methods, while developed on head & neck MRI, are applicable to other body

regions and imaging modalities when trained on the corresponding data.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

Participants will have access to a unique and extensive head & neck MRI dataset derived from the publicly available OpenNeuro collection. This dataset is an amalgamation of over 700 smaller datasets, all published under a permissive CC0/PDDL license. After cleaning and standardization of image format and metadata, the final dataset comprises 114,570 3D volumes from 34,191 patients, making it the largest publicly available head & neck MRI resource to date. The collection contains a variety of MRI sequences, such as T1w, Flair, T2w sequences, as well as apparent diffusion coefficient (ADC) and fractional anisotropy (FA) maps.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

MRI (multiple sequences), Processed Diffusion-weighted MRI ADC and FA maps

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

Along with the image data, we provide predicted foreground masks and anonymization masks [Nohel et al., 2025]. These masks are crucial because some images in the challenge cohort have undergone preprocessing steps, such as brain extraction or anonymization. These preprocessing steps may pose challenges for reconstruction-based SSL methods, making the additional context essential for effective method development.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

We collected and unified all available metadata associated with the images, including sex, handedness, race, health status, image modality, weight, age, and body mass index. However, not all metadata fields are available for every image in the dataset.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The data originates from more than 700 studies within the OpenNeuro collection, encompassing a variety of MRI sequences.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

We intentionally limit details about the downstream tasks to avoid overfitting and to prioritize the development of robust and generalizable self-supervised learning methods. The goal is for participating algorithms to generate versatile feature representations of head and brain structures in MRI scans, spanning various sequences such as T1-weighted, FLAIR, T2-weighted, diffusion coefficient (ADC), and fractional anisotropy (FA) maps.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy,Robustness,Applicability,Usability

DATA SETS**Data source(s)**

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

The challenge data comes from over 700 studies, resulting in a diverse collection of MRI scans acquired using various scanners from different manufacturers. The dataset includes multiple MRI sequences, such as T1w, T2w, ADC, FA, FLAIR, MP2RAGE, SBRef, and TRACE, among others.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

Some of the images in the dataset have already undergone preprocessing, including anonymization and brain extraction; however, corresponding masks are provided to account for these steps. Additionally, T2w images, as well as ADC and FA maps, were generated from 4D diffusion MRI scans.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

The data used in this challenge comes from over 700 studies conducted at various centers and institutes published by the OpenNeuro initiative. Specific details about the centers will be provided alongside the dataset. The downstream datasets will be provided by clinical partners from the University Hospital Bonn and the University Hospital Heidelberg.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

N/A for the pre-training dataset.

For the downstream datasets, annotations were performed manually by clinicians with several years of experience, ensuring high-quality and expert-level labeling.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

A pre-training case corresponds to one unlabeled 3D head & neck MRI scan. For the downstream tasks, we will split the datasets into fine-tuning and test splits. For the classification tasks, we have binary labels, while for the segmentation tasks, we have pixel-level annotations for all target structures (which could be just one structure). Further details on the downstream tasks will not be provided to prevent overfitting and to maintain focus on developing generalizable methods.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

~115,000 volumes for pretraining. For the downstream experiments, we collected multiple different datasets, with different tasks and a varying number of cases.

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The pre-training dataset consists of 114,570 3D volumes from 34,191 patients, with all images available for training. No details on the downstream tasks, including the specific proportions of fine-tuning and test cases, will be provided to prevent overfitting and to maintain the focus on developing methods that generalize well across different applications and downstream dataset sizes.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

N/A, see above

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

N/A, see above

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

For the classification tasks, we have binary labels, while for the segmentation tasks, we have pixel-level annotations for all target structures (which could be also just one target structure). All annotations were performed manually by clinicians with several years of experience, or the result of follow-up examinations for the classification tasks, e.g. from a histopathological examination. We do not have multiple annotations per case.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

N/A: The datasets were obtained from multiple studies and clinics, with annotations completed as part of separate projects. Consequently, a standardized annotation protocol is not available.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Clinicians with several years of experience in the corresponding field.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

N/A

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

See above (DWI images, brain extraction and anonymization)

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter- and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Potential label noise is unlikely to be a significant issue, as the methods will be evaluated on at least six different datasets, which helps to mitigate the impact of any individual errors within a dataset. While inter- and intra-annotator variability can introduce some level of noise, the diversity of tasks and datasets ensures that the evaluation remains robust and reliable. The focus of the challenge is on evaluating the methods across multiple different tasks rather than solving a single specific clinical problem.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

Performance improvements in previous work have been relatively limited, indicating that further significant gains may be challenging to achieve. However, by providing the largest open-source dataset, we aim to enable participants to make meaningful improvements over training from scratch.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

For segmentation tasks, we largely follow the methodology of the Medical Segmentation Decathlon (MSD) [Antonelli et al. 2021]:

Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC) [Dice et al. 1945]: An overlap metric reflecting volumetric agreement between predicted and reference segmentations.

Normalized Surface Distance (NSD) [Nikolov et al. 2021]: A boundary-focused metric assessing how closely the surfaces of predicted and reference segmentations align.

For tasks with multiple class, both DSC and NSD are computed per class. We evaluate and rank methods separately for each metric and each class, then aggregate these ranks (see ranking procedure below). NSD tolerance values will be defined per dataset based on clinical considerations.

For classification tasks, we will use the following two complementary metrics

Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve (AUROC) [Hanley et al. 1982], a standard metric for evaluating classification performance that is threshold independent.

Balanced Accuracy (BA): The average of sensitivity and specificity, which is particularly suitable for imbalanced datasets.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

DSC is widely used in medical image segmentation for its straightforward interpretation of volumetric overlap. NSD complements DSC by focusing on boundary accuracy, which is crucial for many clinical scenarios. Applying them separately, as done in MSD, ensures both volumetric and boundary fidelity are assessed. For classification, using both AUROC and BA provides complementary perspectives: AUROC offers a threshold-independent assessment of discriminative ability, while BA ensures fair evaluation of datasets with imbalances by giving equal importance to each class. This metric selection aligns with the recent recommendations published by Maier-Hein and Reinke et al. [Maier-Hein, Reinke et al. 2024].

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

Ranking procedure:

Per Segmentation Dataset & Per class:

Compute DSC per case.

Compute NSD per case.

Combine classes within each Metric for Segmentation:

For each segmentation dataset, we average the per-class scores to obtain one DSC-based rank and one NSD-based rank for that dataset. Thus, each dataset yields two sets of ranks: one from DSC and one from NSD.

Combine Metrics within each Segmentation Dataset:

After obtaining dataset-level ranks for DSC and NSD, we average these ranks to produce a single overall rank per dataset. This matches the MSD strategy of giving equal importance to both volumetric and boundary performance.

Combine Multiple Segmentation Datasets:

Each segmentation dataset provides one overall rank per algorithm. We average these ranks equally to produce a single "Segmentation Rank" per algorithm.

Combine Metrics for Multiple Classification Datasets:

For classification, the metrics are aggregated across the datasets in a similar manner. We first obtain dataset-level ranks for AUROC and BA, average these two ranks to obtain a single rank per dataset, and finally average ranks across datasets to obtain a "Classification Rank" per algorithm.

Final Combination (Segmentation & Classification):

Finally, we combine the Segmentation Rank and the Classification Rank with equal weight (50% segmentation, 50% classification) to produce the final overall ranking of algorithms.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

If an algorithm fails to produce predictions for any test case within a dataset, it is assigned the worst possible metric for that case. This ensures fairness and discourages incomplete submissions.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

Averaging ranks across tasks and metrics allows us to cleanly aggregate performance across segmentation datasets (with DSC and NSD measured per class) and classification datasets (with AUROC and BA), resulting in an easily interpretable final ranking. By relying on ranks rather than directly combining different metric values, we avoid complexities of metric normalization and weighting. This approach aligns with best practices demonstrated in prior challenges, such as MSD, and ensures that both segmentation and classification tasks contribute evenly to the final result.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

We will characterize ranking stability using a bootstrap approach [Maier-Hein, Eisenmann et al. 2018 ;Wiesenfarth et al. 2021]. In this method, we repeatedly sample test cases with replacement to form bootstrap samples and re-compute the rankings. By examining the distribution of rankings across these bootstrap samples, we gain insight into how sensitive the final rankings are to the particular test set composition. We will adapt the

open-source “challengeR” toolkit [Wiesenfarth et al. 2021] to facilitate this analysis.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

The bootstrap is a nonparametric technique that makes minimal assumptions, allowing robust estimation of how rankings vary with sampling variability. This approach is recommended in the literature [Wiesenfarth et al. 2021] and does not introduce unnecessary complexity, making it well-suited for assessing the reliability of our final rankings.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

As described above, we will assess ranking variability using the bootstrap-based approach. By examining how the rankings change across bootstrap resamples, we can gauge their robustness.

After the challenge, we will perform additional analyses using the submitted methods to assess convergence time and performance in low-data regimes. These analyses, while important, are not included in the challenge assessment to reduce complexity.

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

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Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

N/A